

inhabited by about 160.000 people (50.000 Turks, 85.000 Jews and 25.000 Greeks). In 1928 the Greeks were 140.000 out of 250.000 of the city's population. Thus, the city became predominantly Greek and the Jews that were previously the majority, they became in a few years time a tiny minority; their size as a community had also been drastically reduced after the WWII; they gradually adapted to the life-styles of Greeks acquiring their own language as well as social behaviour. Today they are a very small minority; they still have some of their old synagogues and retain to a certain extent their ethnic consciousness; however, they participate to the city's public life and affairs in the same way as the Greeks do.

The second influx happened when, after the WWII many rural workers invaded as migrants to the city seeking for jobs in the developing industrial sector. Between 1940 and 1970 the city's population doubled; this increase of the Greek population further reduced the percentage of Jews in the new city.

Both influxes resulted in a condensed "intra-muros" city. The economy of the city flourished, the commercial areas and market places inside the walls began to expand.

In the 1970s high ratios of employment concentration indicate that Thessalonika becomes the most important, after Athens, pole of the country's development, specialising mainly in wholesale commerce and industrial-manufacture sectors. Its influence expanded in whole Macedonia and Thrace.

Now the city is an export and import trade centre, responsible for over 1/3 of the whole country's trade, an important industrial centre for northern Greece, an educational and transport centre with its railway station and airport, the harbour with storage facilities and customs

offices, light industry and manufacture; there is also a rapid growth of the business and tertiary sector, that is the banking system, insurance companies and offices.

The developing capitalist mode of production that resulted to the division of labour as the fundamental organising principle of the society, contributed to the emergence of social groups differentiated by the persons roles and positions in the system of production (manual labourers, industrial workers, white-collar office workers, high-level management personnel etc). The documentary evidence available suggests that the city within-the-walls is still occupied by housing differentiated spatially according to social classes referred above.

The prevailing patterns of population distribution is a functional specialisation among the northern, eastern and southeastern communities. There has to be noticed a polarisation between the eastern districts gathering the upper-income social classes and the western ones where there is an almost absolute absence of middle class.

Concerning homogenisation, there is one dominant culture with slight differences. Social relations in the neighbourhood scale are not strong. There is also a lack of pluralism in the social processes and institutions produced by the civil society, that is a lack of voluntary associations through which local needs could be expressed, local culture developed and local social integration realised.

The distribution of social groups remains almost constant, despite of the trends of population increase (map 4). Landowners and the upper class achieved to keep their premises close to C.B.D., while the middle class lives in the mixed residential areas between Egnatia St. and "Ano-Polis", being the most pressured by the expanding C.B.D. The low and lower income population as well as the old refugees and their descendants are

accommodated in "Ano-Polis" that largely remained a purely residential area.

There have been also documented great differences in the frequency of movements toward and from the city centre. With regards to recreation, the frequency is greater for the eastern districts than for the western ones. Concerning shopping, there is a double antithesis between a) the eastern and western sectors and b) between the quasi-central western sectors and the most decentralised western ones: in the eastern districts the relatively good services of retailing reduce the movement to the centre; by contrast, the city-centre attracts the residents of the western districts for the daily shopping; b) the residents of the most decentralised western districts perform a great degree of dependence from the city-centre, even for their daily shopping activities.

Furthermore, there are the "temporary" residents of the city (i.e. University students, civil workers). There is also a remarkably low percentage of the agricultural migrant population among the permanent residents of the "intra-muros" city (0.81%) that, nevertheless, are part of its visiting group.

Concluding, the city in the mid 1970s and late 1980s consists of a homogeneous Greek population and a tiny minority of Jews adapted to the Greek culture.

It maintains strong transpatial links and attracts through its central-area functions the overall metropolitan region and a much broader area in Macedonia.

These links are not just trading and administration activities as they used to be in the 1917 city, but a continual flow of people realised via their physical movement in and out of it, in addition to trading and other

transpatial organisations mentioned above.

Therefore, the city is not any more a self-contained system, but it depends on and serves a whole metropolitan area.

There is an almost strict distribution of population on income lines; the eastern areas are occupied by the rich while the western ones by the poor. Rich also reside close to the C.B.D., the middle class between Egnatia and "Ano-Polis" and the poor in "Ano-Polis".

The links as flows of people between the residential areas and the city-core differ according to income; the eastern high-income areas maintain strong connections with the core, while the western quasi-central ones weaker. The links are stronger for farther western areas where there is a remarkable lack of any central-area functions.

The city has also a great deal of "temporary" residents and visitors.

Moreover, there is one prevailing culture with slight differences and lack of pluralism in social processes and institutions.

In general, the social system during the modern and post-modern ages works mainly on the non-correspondence model, with asymmetric and non-distributed structure with respect to the differentiated low and middle social classes.

CHAPTER IV: THE SPATIAL ORGANISATION

4.1. The 1890 Plan

4.2. The 1891 Plan.

4.3. The 1917 Plan

4.4. The mid 1970s Plan

4.5. The late 1980s Plan

4.1. The 1890 Plan

The structure of the city had been stabilised in the late seventeenth century (map 4). A basic characteristic is the desegregation of the prevailing ethnicities to separate city-quarters. This trend was so powerful that the city-quarters gained to a large extent their identity along ethnical lines (map 5). The beginning of this ethnographic desegregation was facilitated by the domination of the "closed" trade-unions economy and the low grade of commercialisation.

The commercial centre was initially allocated at two parts, one along Egnatia and St.Sophia's Sts. There also existed the trade union's markets at "Misir Tsarsi" (Ladadika), the area around the port with tannery manufactures (100 units), the "Tahtul Kale" market beneath the frontiers and "Kapani" market (map 6).

The part of the city below St. Demetrious St. is the most lively and busy area of the town, due to its commercial character. Egnatia St., apart from being the main "through axis" of the city, and therefore, used as entrance and exit by merchants and visitors, provided a lot of accommodation and entertainment facilities to the city's visitors.

The harbour was a very busy area, too, and its quays were always full of merchants, shop keepers, sailors and so on.

In the late Ottoman period there were 12 Greek, 43 Turkish and 16 Jewish quarters (map 7). In broad terms, the city was occupied at its upper part ("Ano-Polis") mostly by the Turks. The "intra-muros" central and southeastern part belonged to the Greek quarters, the central and lower part close to the sea was occupied by the Jews, while in the southwestern part there had been a quarter belonging to "levantines" - merchants from Europe. Among the Jews there existed two quarters

belonging to the Greek community and one among the Turkish quarters in "Ano-Polis".

The lower parts were the public areas of the city, with shops and administration buildings like the government centre.

The Turkish quarters at the hilly part of the city were decentralised neighbourhoods with narrow, winding, quiet and secluded streets, paths and dead-ends leading to spacious and luxurious residences.

The residential areas of the affluent Jews, Greeks and agents from Europe, still not differentiated from the "down-town" area competed to gain an easy accessibility to the market area and at the same time they belonged to their ethnically distinguished city-quarters.

The Jews were accommodated between the harbour and Egnatia St., mostly in the area burnt in 1890 and replanned in 1891.

The Greeks were the most oppressed group by the Turks; the latter had deprived them from the most magnificent byzantine churches that converted them to mosques. They clustered around the remaining 12 or 15 smaller churches in the south-eastern part of the city. The churches, hidden from the main streets, served as places for refuge and intimacy, as well as educational centres and meeting places for the Greek population; it is to be remarked that most of them were not free-standing, but embodied to the surrounding buildings (maps 8 and 9).

Three different principles seem to have prevailed in the organisation of the urban space according to the three cultures and life-styles. Desire for seclusion and strict separation of their residences from the rest of the city for the Turks and at the same time allocation of their administration buildings along main streets close to the centre of the city, with easy accessibility from the outside; for the Jews the desire for being in the centre of the commercial activity and public interaction; finally, for the

Greeks a defensive as well as protective clustering around their christian churches.

Concerning the street network, there is a remarkable continuity of the main axes that refer to the city's original plan. Egnatia St. continues to be the prevailing distributor of movements (the "decumanus"), while Venizelou St. (the "cardo") the administration street accommodating the Town Hall and guilds houses.

The city-quarters were initially defined by the major axes of the city and its walls; the condensation of the "intra-muros" population led to the decrease of their size and increase of their number, but the compatibility of their boundaries with the main axes of the "regular" pattern of the city had been clearly maintained. The intra-quarter street network was primarily irregular characterised by curvilinear or/and winding distributor streets and impasses formatted all along the urbanisation process.

The mosques were at the intersecting point of the main street network, while the Greek social centres could be found in the heart of the "insulae".The Jewish synagogues had a direct accessibility from the street.

4.2 The 1891 Plan

The growth of the middle class facilitated the industrial development of the city: the city-core began to perform a range of tertiary sector activities being differentiated from market area expanding along Egnatia, St. Sophia's and Venizelou Sts. A major focal point was also around St.Minas, the mixed commercial and retailing centre of the city. At the dock-area between the coast and the up-to-date Frangon St. there were warehouses and wholesale markets. Around the core and the market areas manufacture and industry were allocated. After 1913 the Greeks

and Jews competed to occupy the most accessible places around the city-core where retailing expanded rapidly.

The first industrial units were settled at the area between the new railway lines and the harbour (map 10).

The condensation of the "intra-muros" city was followed by the rapid development of the "extra-muros" areas at the city's eastern and southern parts and a simultaneous social class desegregation.

Between 1912-17 in the "intra-muros" city the strong dependence of the urban structure on ethnicity, occupation and family ties were still retained.

In terms of spatial transformations, there were created, opened or/and aligned 5 basic arteries, penetrating the historical nucleus (map 11).

After the 1890 fire, a new plan for the Jewish area heavily damaged by the fire was elaborated. The comparing of the two plans before and after the fire (1882-83 and 1915-17) proves

- the differentiation of the street network (maps 12,13,14,15)
- the diversification of the "insulae" (fig.160).

The basic logic of the 1891 plan was the rationalisation of the urban space; the transition from the public to the private realm became more direct (maps 8.a and 8.b);the significance was transferred from the "insula" to the street network.

This basic diversification in the space organisation indicates the differentiation at the level of social stratification and thus, the redesign of this area performs a significant step toward the transformation of the traditional city-structure comprehended after the 1917 fire (map 17).

Concluding, the pre-1917 city is a market oriented city where housing and light manufacture compete to gain easy accessibility to market areas;

an indication of that is the existence of the main entrances of the city along the main parallel St. Demetrious and Egnatia Sts strongly related to market areas and offering direct accessibility to merchants and the city's visitors.

The different principles that prevailed in the culture of the three ethnicities produced a diversified urban space, especially in residential areas, where a) for the Greeks defensive as well as protective clustering, seclusion isolation from the external world contributed to social interaction along ethnic lines, b) for the Turks their isolation in "Ano-Polis" indicated their power as a ruling class and their public buildings along the main axes of the "down-town" area confirming their dominance and c) the Jews' proximity to the market centre and public interaction sacrificing every rule of hygiene and convenience.

The city's initial major orthogonal pattern still served as a "grid" differentiating the "ethnoquarters".

The centres of the quarters exemplify three major typologies of social centres according to their ethnical origins: the social/religious centre at the intersecting point of the quarters' street network, b) the centre hidden in the "insula" and c) the centre scattered indifferently in the insula, but always with a direct accessibility from the street.

Hence, the "intra-muros" residential areas offered the image of a self-generated, unplanned, "organically-grown" urban tissue including mainly areas with mixed land-uses and not differentiating housing from central-area functions.

The typology of the urban tissue has essentially remained the same up to 1917, with numerous small additive alterations providing the pre-capitalistic "multi-ethnic" city with a mosaic character of ethnical-and-cultural neighbourhood-units linked to the loose street network.

The modernisation attempted in 1891 was the first step toward the city's spatial transformation.

4.3. The 1917 Plan

The plan is influenced by the "City-Beautiful" and "Garden-City" movements as well as the "Modern Planning", already tracing its experimental stage in developing Europe (maps 18,19).

In the new plan there is an attempt to adapt the old, unaffected by the fire areas to the new principles, a differentiation of land-uses, and an introduction of new articulative elements (maps 20,20.a). The classification of the axes of monuments, unified administrative centre, allocation of functions in some specific zones and the revealing of special public buildings (or monuments) are some basic guide-lines for the city's development and expansion.

The city's new form is articulated to the main axes linking it with its hinterland and the international network, the emphasis stressed on the expected dominance of the vehicle-oriented traffic and the allocation of specific facilities it required (map 21).

The neoclassical principles set by the Greek ruling class and the planner indicate the insistence on the ideal of the "mono-centric" city that at its gravity centre there were allocated administration, financial, social and cultural activities (map 22).

In the modern "extra-muros" suburbs there are allocated industries, the harbour, warehouses, the railway stations as well as low income housing

for the accommodation of the working population.

The eastern part is designed as a residential area for the upper class and recreation area for the whole city.

Between the eastern "extra-muros" city and the city-core there are proposed extensive parks and the city's University.

The whole of the designed city-core is exposed to the city's visitors through its penetration by all the main axes that used to exist in the old city.

The commercial and retailing activities are allocated linearly along the main axes linking the city with its periphery. The linear model of city's expansion collaborates with the concentric allocation of central-area functions: the two main arteries articulate the whole urban form (Egnatia and Aristotelous Sts in map 23).

In general, it has been attempted a comprehensive reformulation of the pre-existing urban tissue. The pre-existing orthogonal grid pattern is combined with the radial-and-concentric tracing so that starting from points of some significance (i.e. monuments) or transportation nodes (i.e. squares) to create a system of diagonal and orthogonal streets and reveal some of the Greek monuments as points of reference (fig.24).

To the existing main boulevards it is added a fourth one (Tsimiskis St.). In the most significant intersecting points there are opened "rond-points" or ellipsoid broadenings and monumental perspectives. The parallel streets that contribute to the distribution of movements are cut by perpendicular ones occupied by different functions (Venizelou and St. Sophia's Sts: commercial, Aristotelous and Dem.Gounaris Sts: administrative, cultural, recreational).

There are created new monumental wholenesses and perspectives with "neoclassical principles (fig. 25).The urban character and Greek ethnic

identity of the city are emphasised through the creation of a monumental boulevard perpendicular to the coast linking two squares with central-area functions. Functional and symbolic links are used in order to stress the emphasis on the significance of the general allocation (Aristotelous St.).

Hebrard, ignoring the existence of the ancient Agora (excavated in 1966), allocates the city-centre at its initial site (fig.26). The large "place civique" upwards Egnatia St. has got a political and administration character (fig 27). There are allocated symmetrically the Town Hall and the Court House of the city, while higher there are symmetrically developed buildings with public uses. The square defined by arcades and colonnades occupies a large surface and is designed to operate for national and local festivals, as well as political meetings.

Toward Egnatia St. two smaller squares are created. When the administration centre seises operating, the focus of public life is transferred to Aristotelous sq. (close to the coast). This second square is the focus of commercial and tourist activities, the shops with luxury goods, hotels and bars (fig. 28). The urbanist's inspirations are referred to the influence of Priene's classical Plan including a wholeness of three squares with different activities (political, commercial and food market).

Reviving the Galerian complex, Hebrard proposes an archaeological promenade along the procedural boulevard linking Rotonda, Hippodrome, the Roman palace and the Octagon where the findings from the excavations are linked to a complex of walkways and squares (map 24). This new synthesis allocates Rotonda at the centre of a wide square, where there converge radially-traced streets in the pattern of the parisian Arc de Triumph. The square of Hippodrome represents the roman amphitheatre.

Nevertheless, there are many areas where the existing wholenesses are

not compatible with the proposed tracings (Frangomachalas and Ladadika in fig. 29).

In "Ano-Polis" and wherever a proposal for new tracings takes place (e.g. close to the city's walls) there prevails the attitude that the old structure has to be adapted to the new one and not the opposite.

Concluding, the intervention altered drastically the spatial structure of the city. The traditional organisation into quarters and their internal articulation, the spatial co-existence of all the income and professional ranks were overturned. The Greek, Jewish and Turkish neighbourhoods were replaced by areas of low, middle and high income classes. There is an explicit shift from the type of the communal enclosed neighbourhood with particular cultural characteristics to the open, "european" type of the building block (map 30).

One of the primary concerns of the plan had been to increase the links with the outside world articulating along them the main commercial activities. It is the first application of the zoning system on the ground (residential areas differentiated according to income and central-area functions desegregated from housing).

The geometrical characteristics of the urban space come out of a reconsidered orthogonal grid pattern enriched by diagonal tracings, monumental perspectives and an elaborated system of squares and open spaces. There were selectively adopted elements from the hellenistic and roman grid pattern of the city and there were "revealed" in isolated and conspicuous sites the most important public buildings.

The interaction and relationships of complementarity between the articulating components of the pre-existing urban tissue -the quarter, the street, the square, the building block- were simplified, while new

monumental squares and boulevards were created.

The Greek ethnical identity was attempted to be strengthened. New monumental wholenesses and perspectives were created with "neoclassical" principles and new range of uses was articulated to the spatial structure. The Plan emphasised the links with the glorious past of the Greek and Roman history, while eliminating the witnesses of the other two cultures that developed along centuries in the city.

The "rationalisation" of the urban space was enhanced through classified wide streets for the traffic, unified in size building blocks, rectangularity and abolition of dead-ends.

4.4 The mid 1970s Plan

The city's transformation after 1920 was heavily influenced by the planning policies exercised in the whole country.

The city's first Development Plan in 1968 had been partially implemented due to the radical transformations it suggested (extensive application of zoning principles).

One of the weakest points of that plan was the proposal the city to develop a number of poles that would counterbalance the development of the city's main C.B.D. The twenty years that have passed proved that no such centres can compete in effectiveness and efficiency the existing C.B.D. (map 31).

Now the C.B.D. consists of three successive zones (the C.B.D. core, a residual of C.B.D. and a transitional zone) dominated by offices, banks, insurance companies, retail and wholesale commerce, light manufacturing

and a small percentage of education, recreation and health services (Ph.1. and map 32). Moreover, there has been noticed a trend for the C.B.D. to expand south-eastward and north-westward.

Commerce occupies a certain percentage of land in all three zones-with a slight reduction in the medium one; the tertiary sector is reduced systematically toward the periphery of C.B.D., while manufacture increases. The activity is differentiated: eastward Aristotelous St. and all along Tsimiskis St. the commerce of luxury goods, west-wards the periodical and scarce commerce.

The offices are mainly allocated west-wards Aristotelous St. with a greater concentration in Ionos Dragoumis, Hermou, Aristotelous, Metropoleos and Tsimiskis Sts; trends for their expansion are westwards.

Retailing dominates in the ground floors of the buildings in the area between Democratias sq. up to Aggelakis St. (maps 33 and 35).

South-eastward, north-westwards and out of the C.B.D. there happens the expansion of retailing and the tertiary sector where they replace wholesale, warehouses and workshops; this sets the danger housing to disappear from whole city-districts.

East-ward Chalkeon St. and north-wards Egnatia St. there are mixed retailing and housing, similar to the eastern parts of the city.

The clothe-manufacturing and the corresponding retailing are at Valaoritou, Ptolemaeon, Ionos Dragoumis and the northwestern section of Antigonidon Sts; there is the centre of the ready-made clothes for the whole metropolitan area and a region broader than that.

In general, manufacturing and industry are allocated along Vas. Heracliou, I.Dragoumis, Philippou, Deoeceteriou, Dodekanessou, Anageneseos, Giannitson, Monasteriou St. and Democratias sq. The accessories are between Langadas, Monasteriou and M. Kalos sts. Industry

is also allocated close to the big transportation nodes, the city's entrances and the working population residential areas.

The whole-sale food-market is allocated in Ladadika, Modiano, Vlalis, Vatikiotis areas (Ph.2,3,4,5,6,7.). There is also a fish market in the port and a meat market in Modiano.

The Court Houses are allocated at the south-western part of the city (28th October St.). In the same building block there are accommodated some public services such as health and telecommunications. Opposite to the Court Houses and close to Egnatia St. there are numerous coach-stations linking the city and the whole metropolitan area with other cities and regions.

"Ano-Polis" urban tissue is based on the 1931 plan that proposed numerous transformations of the street network ignoring its pre-existing social and spatial morphology (Ph.8,9,10). Now it continues to be a residential area where the central-area functions concern mainly the provision of facilities for local purposes (map 35). The main focuses of these activities -commerce, education and recreation -are a) along D.Poleorkitis, Kleious, Papadopoulou and Acritas Sts, b) Theophilou, Acropoleos, Athinas, Agias Sophias Sts, c) along Olympiados St. and d) Proteos, Androkidou Sts and Kallitheas sq. Recreation is also noticed at Tsinari and Cafe Coule, Terpsitheas sq. and Heptapyrgiou st. (map 36).

Light manufacturing is scattered all over the area, points of major concentration are in the western part of Olympiados St., Elephsinos St., the streets around Terpsitheas sq. and the intersecting point between Athinas and Theotokopoulou Sts.

4.5. The late 1980s Plan

Post-modern city-planning in Greece emerged in the late 70s and was legitimated by the 947/1979 and later the 1337/83 Acts.

In Thessalonika the multinuclear organisation of the whole metropolitan area is encouraged. The city within-the-walls is proposed to develop as the "down-town" area of the whole metropolis. Thus, an increased flow of people is expected to take place from the outskirts to the city and vice versa (map 37). The retainment of housing and its mixture with the central-area functions is primarily encouraged in order to keep "alive" the urban public space.

The C.B.D. is encouraged to expand beyond the city's borders themselves where zoning system seems to dominate. Here city-inhabitants cannot have a clear image of it and visitors are accessed to it before entering the city itself.

Within the walls, the mix of uses is accompanied by their refinement; wholesale, manufacture and industry are prohibited, reallocated at the periphery and close to the main transportation networks.

In the old market of Ladadika as well as the designed ones of Vlais-Vatikiotis-Pazarakia, the uses are confined to retailing.

The monuments, monumental wholenesses, major public open spaces and commercial streets-especially the old ones- are proposed to be linked with pedestrian networks, not compulsorily at the same level with the vehicle circulation (map.38).

The three proposed major "monumental promenades" vertical to the coast or along the city-frontiers are a) along Aristotelous St. from the coast up to Osios David and Moni Vlatadon, b) the Galerian complex from the coast along the eastern city-frontiers up to Heptapyrgion, c) from the

old western frontiers of "Top-Hane" to Ste Aekaterinis ch., and then all along the north-western frontiers, as well as a local promenade linking Ste Sophia with Acheropeoetus and St. Athanasious chs. The two eastern wholenesses are linked through the pedestrianisation of Nikis blrd along the coast that is expected to receive the major density of pedestrian movement (map 39).

The markets referred above are designated as ZEE zones (zones for incentives and special treatment, map 3). Through the above mechanisms it is expected that these areas will gain a greater variety of uses and better public infrastructure attracting inhabitants and visitors along them.

The spatial organisation of the city is revealed in map 40.

"Ano-Polis" remains under the 1979 plan.

The major part of the city within-the-walls by becoming the location of intense commercial and service activities, it has also become the "locus" of interaction between the city's inhabitants among themselves and the inhabitants and visitors as well. This applies first to the centralised market areas that attract people from all over the city and its carrier and to a less extent to the sector of services, that all the more grows independently of the site.

Up to the mid seventies, the tertiary sector tended to focus on special locations maintaining direct links with the sector it serviced: In the late 80s physical proximity seems to play all the less important role to the allocation of central-area activities, especially the C.B.D. core, at the most accessible places.

**5. CHAPTER V: OVERALL REVIEW OF VALUES OF SPATIAL
VARIABLES**

5.1. O Order measures

5.2. A Order measures

5.3. B Order measures

5. Overall review of values of spatial variables

5.1. O order measures

5.1.1. Grid Axiality (GA) and Line-Link ratio (LLR)

	1	2	3
CODE/PLAN	No of streets=L	No of links=N	LLR=N/L
THESSCITY.1	1012	1756	1.735
THESSCITY.3	951	1805	1.898
THESSCITY.4	827	1899	2.296
THESSCITY.5	706	1500	2.125
THESSUP.3	306	507	1.657
THESSUP.4	341	570	1.672
THESSUP.5	327	536	1.639
THESSGR.1	165	258	1.564
THESSTUR.1	562	918	1.633
THESSJEW.1	240	397	1.654
MARKET.1-2	150	283	1.887
M1. 1-2	40	70	1.75
M2. 1-2	70	137	1.957

Table 1: Streets (L), Street-Links (N) and Line-Link Ratio (LLR=N/L).

THESSCITY 1-2 : The city's plan in 1890
 THESSCITY 3 : The plan before the 1917-fire
 THESSCITY 4 : The neoclassical plan in 1917
 THESSCITY 5 : The plan in the mid '70s
 THESSUP 1-2-3 : "Ano-Polla" before the 1917 fire
 THESSUP 4 : " " after " " "
 THESSUP 5 : " " in the mid '70s
 THESSGR 1-2 :
 THESSTUR 1-2 : The city's "E"quarters
 THESSJEW 1-2 :
 M1, M2 (1-2): Market areas in the pre-1917 city

There is a remarkable alteration of the number of streets in the successive plans of 1891, 1917 and 1988 (21 more lines between 1890 and 1891 and 431 lines less between 1891 and 1988). The lines lost in the transition from the "unplanned" to the "neoclassical" plan are 410 and from the neoclassical to the "modern" one are 121. Total number of lost lines 531, that is 35.2% of the total initial lines; therefore, the system as a whole has been affected drastically in terms of its open space network mainly by the neoclassical plan and to a less extent by the 1891 and modern plans. (Table I, columns 1,2). More precisely, "Ano-Polis" was designed in 1917 to acquire 35 more streets and up to now it has acquired 26 of them; therefore, the major loss of streets concerns the lower part of the city, first designed in 1917.

LLR fluctuates between $1.564 < LLR < 1.957$ in the "unplanned" city whereas in the "planned" city of 1917 and late 1980s LLR is $2.125 < LLR < 2.296$. Consequently, the structures of THESSCITY. 1-2 and THESSCITY. 3 are typologically close to the structure of small towns ($1.5 < LLR < 1.6$) and "organic" towns ($1.8 < LLR < 2.10$) whereas THESSCITY.4 and THESSCITY.5 close to a neoclassical and modern structure ($2.10 < LLR < 3.1$, table I, column 3).

Although this study is not concerned with the non-distributed lines, it can be referred here that there is a reduction in their number from THESSCITY. 1-2 to THESSCITY. 3 (67 dead-ends less in the latter plan). Therefore, the pre-1891 plan is slightly more regularised than the "organic" plan of 1890 (table 2, column 3). The dead-ends are all the more reduced up to the modern plan (the urban system all the more rationalised).

GA of THESSCITY. 1-2 gets values between $0.1626 < GA < 0.3312$ and THESSCITY. 3 between $0.1626 < GA < 0.4209$, that is THESSCITY. 3 turns to be slightly more gridiron than THESSCITY. 1-2 (the higher values are acquired in the replanned neighbourhoods in 1891 TQ6, TQ7, TQ20, column 4). In table 2, GA varies: $0.2439 < GAg < 0.5882$, $0.1626 < GAt < 0.3312$,

0.223<GAj<0.6667, 0.2056<GAm<0.2963. The lowest value is in the Turkish quarters (GAt=0.1626) and the highest one in the Jewish quarters (GAj=0.6667): The Turkish quarters are the least and the Jewish ones the most gridiron areas (column 5).

0	1	2	3	4
	L	N	ND	I
TQ1	34	49	13/12	10
TQ2	89	164	32/30	39
TQ3	40	53	27/22	10
TQ4	42	71	15/13	12
TQ5	62	94	25/30	21
TQ6	31/36	53/64	6/7	18/20
TQ7	17/26	39/48	1/1	18/20
TQ8	18	37	7/1	25
TQ9	50	86	5/4	38
TQ10	61	126	1/1	47
TQ11	27	35	-/-	9
TQ12	42	97	18/17	11
TQ13	58	80	28/24	20
TQ14	54	76	29/26	18
TQ15	53	76	35/34	14
TQ16	70	102	27/23	22
TQ17	50	86	13/12	13
TQ18	41	59	17/15	20
TQ19	39	54	14/13	25
TQ20	39/46	57/70	16/9	18/20

TQ21	33	69	27/2	19
TQ22	53	90	6/6	24
TQ23	50	83	./1	30
TQ24	37	59	4/3	21
TQ25	32	40	22/24	12
TQ26	35	58	19/9	23
TQ27	38	60	12/13	16
TQ28	42	62	18/18	17
TOTAL	1012/	2020/	437/	571/
	1032	2048	370.	574.

	5	6	7
0	GA	LLR	Ethn.
TQ1	0.2448	1.441	G
TQ2	0.1628	1.843	T
TQ3	0.2081	1.325	T
TQ4	0.2126	1.691	T
TQ5	0.1801	1.516	T
TQ6	0.29/0.36	1.78/1.87	G
TQ8	0.667	2.056	J
TQ9	0.2866	1.720	J
TQ10	0.2576	2.066	J
TQ11	0.2963	1.296	M
TQ12	0.2056	2.309	T
TQ13	0.1824	1.379	T

TQ14	0.1942	1.407	T
TQ15	0.1789	1.434	T
TQ16	0.1626	1.457	T
TQ17	0.2247	1.720	T
TQ18	0.2669	1.439	T
TQ19	0.3077	1.385	G
TQ20	0.268/0.238	1.462/1.522	T
TQ21	0.3248	2.091	J
TQ22	0.2230	1.698	J
TQ23	0.2591	1.660	M
TQ24	0.3018	1.595	J
TQ25	0.2791	1.250	T
TQ26	0.3312	1.657	T
TQ27	0.2632	1.579	T
TQ28	0.2439	1.476	G
TOTAL	0.041/0.04	1.63/1.63	

Table 2. Order measures of THESSITY.1-2 and THESSCITY. 3 (/).

TQ : City neighbourhoods

L : No of distributed lines

N : No of links

ND : No of non -distributed lines

I : No of islands or building blocks

GA : Grid axiality or regularity ratio

LLR : Line link ratio , LLR=N/L

$GA = \frac{\sqrt{IX^2} + 2}{L}$, GA=1 ->perfect grid

L

LLR is low for "Ano-Polis" while for the lower part of the city it increases after the 1981 plan. The values for the "organic" parts are $1.250 < LLR < 2.309$ and for the planned quarters $1.522 < LLR > 2.294$ and therefore, there is an increase of LLR in the replanned quarters. The mean LLR decreases slightly from 1.633 to 1.628: the 0.005 shift is very slight and thus, the structure can be argued that typologically remains largely stable, close to the structure of the "unplanned", "organic" cities. With respect to the three ethnicities, $1.385 < LLR_g < 2.294$, $1.250 < LLR_t < 1.843$, $1.595 < LLR_j < 2.091$, $1.296 < LLR_m < 2.309$. The lowest value is in the Turkish areas (LLR=1.250) and the highest one in the market areas (LLR=2.309): the least regularised are the Turkish areas, then the Jewish, the Greek and finally, the most regularised are the market areas (column 6).

	a1	b1	b1		a3	b3	c3	c1-c3
	L	ND	%		L	ND	%	%
THESSTUR	703	317	45%	THESS	710	275	38.73	6.27
THESSGR	163	53	32.52%	T				
THESSJEW	252	50	32.52%	THESS	177	51	28.81	3.71
M.1-2	119	18	15.13%	G				
TOTAL	1012	437	43.18%	THESS	252	14	5.6	14.28
				J				
				M.3	119	18	15.13	0.2
				TOTAL	1032	370	35.85	7.3

Table 2.1 ND%L in THESSCITY .1-2

Table 2.2: ND%L in THESSCITY.3

The percentage of non-distributed lines with respect to the whole system is reduced from 30.16% in THESSCITY. 1-2 to 26.39% in THESSCITY. 3. The major reduction happened in the Jewish area and this is due to the 1891 plan. The Turkish areas have the most dead-ends (higher than the average) and the Greek ones follow. The most "compact" building blocks are found in market and Jewish areas and this is enhanced by the 1891 plan (tables 2.1 and 2.2.).

The plans of THESSCITY. 4 and THESSCITY. 5 are divided in the same number of areas (now planning units) coinciding with the old neighbourhood -or "ethnoquarter"- boundaries wherever there had been minor alterations (i.e. "Ano-Polis") and approximately the same surface where there is a complete transformation of the urban tissue (i.e. Lower City).

In THESSCITY.4 Grid Axiality (GA) gets values between $0.172 < GA < 0.476$, that is it becomes even more gridiron than the pre-1917 plan (table 3, column 5). The Line Link ratio (LLR) fluctuates between $1.38 < LLR < 3.000$: the city is within the limits of the neoclassical plan, "Ano-Polis" maintaining again the lowest values. The neoclassical plan alters the city's spatial morphology even at the micro-scale of the planning unit (column 6).

In THESSCITY. 5, $1.51 < GA < 0.588$, that is the gridiron slightly increases, but not as much as in the neoclassical plan (table 4, column 5). In the same plan $1.25 < LLR < 2.29$, that is the neoclassical attributes are reduced remarkably, but nevertheless, the ratio remains within the limits of the modern plan (column 6).

	1	2	3	4	5	6
	L	N	ND	I	GA	LLR
TQ1	34	47	9	10	0.3	1.4
TQ2	82	152	27	41	0.2	1.9
TQ3	44	61	8	15	0.2	1.4
TQ4	35	58	-	18	0.3	1.7
TQ5	47	81	-	21	0.24	1.7
TQ6	34	63	-	24	0.4	1.9
TQ7	16	30	-	12	0.6	1.9
TQ8	26	51	-	18	0.4	2.0
TQ9	26	51	-	24	0.5	2.0
TQ10	18	32	-	18	0.6	1.6
TQ11	28	53	1	21	0.4	1.9
TQ12	33	67	4	19	0.3	2.0
TQ13	44	78	2	29	0.3	1.8
TQ14	64	100	13	24	0.1	1.6
TQ15	66	93	20	22	0.2	1.4
TQ16	67	112	24	25	0.2	1.7
TQ17	41	59	9	14	0.2	1.5
TQ18	33	59	5	20	0.3	1.8
TQ19	33	57	-	21	0.3	1.7
TQ20	33	57	-	17	0.3	1.7
TQ21	29	55	1	29	0.4	1.9
TQ22	29	60	2	28	0.4	1.9
TQ23	32	96	-	21	0.4	2.1
TQ24	32	52	-	17	0.3	3.0

TQ25	29	42	-	11	0.3	2.9
TQ26	21	38	-	16	0.5	1.8
TQ27	41	77	-	22	0.3	1.9
TQ28	27	58	-	24	0.4	2.2

Table 3. O Order measures of THESSCITY.4

The mean GA and LLR are reduced slightly in THESSCITY.3 and then there is a remarkable increase in both of them, MGA approaching 1.00 (perfect grid) and LLR exceeding 2.00 (lower threshold of LLR for the neoclassical and modern plans).

In THESSCITY. 4 there can be noticed a further reduction and in a THESSCITY. 5 a new reduction (6.24% of its non-distributed lines). In the transition from the "unplanned" to the modern plan the urban system has lost 31.59% of its distributed lines and 89.25% of its non-distributed lines.

5.2. A Order measures

5.2.1 Depth and Relative Asymmetry

The 1891 and 1917 plans increase the connectivity (CON) of the system whereas the modern plan slightly reduces it; the city after the Neoclassical plan acquires better CON than the average (3.60). The CON increase for "Ano-Polis" is smaller, but stable and lower than the average. In the pre-1917 plan the lower CON is noticed in the Greek quarters and the higher one in the market areas (table 5, column 6).

MMD and MRRA are decreased drastically from the "unplanned" to the "planned" city (table 5, columns 1,2). The MMD for the whole city is reduced by 1.58 while the MMD of "Ano-Polis" (THESSUP.1-2,3,4) by 0.65 from the pre-1917 plans to the 1917 plan: the neoclassical plan reduced the mean depth of the whole city, especially the lower part of it. The same applies to MRRA: only THESSCITY.1-2 has MRRA higher than the mean RRA of urban lay-outs (0.93); reduction by 0.18 from the "unplanned" to the neoclassical plan and increase by 0.06 from the neoclassical to the modern one: the neoclassical plan integrated best the city's parts to the whole, while there is a slight inverse trend in the modern plan. In "Ano-Polis" MMD and MRRA are continually reduced up to the modern plan: there is an increasing integration of this part of the city to the whole .

The reduction of MMD and MRRA for "Ano-Polis" indicates that the area has become far more integrated now than in the pre-1917 plans. The greatest reduction happened with the neoclassical plan [tables 7(a),(b) and 8(a),(b)], that is "Ano-Polis" becomes all the more integrated to the overall structure. Generally, the neoclassical plan integrates better

	1	2	3	4	5	6
	L	N	ND	I	CA	LLR
TQ1	34	49	-	15	0.3	1.5
TQ2	89	164	-	45	0.2	1.8
TQ3	40	53	3	20	0.3	1.3
TQ4	42	71	1	22	0.3	1.7
TQ5	62	94	4	26	0.2	1.5
TQ6	31	58	-	23	0.4	1.9
TQ7	17	39	-	16	0.6	2.3
TQ8	18	37	-	14	0.5	2.1

TQ9	47	86	-	27	0.3	1.8
TQ10	61	126	-	13	0.2	2.1
TQ11	27	35	1	11	0.3	1.3
TQ12	42	57	1	31	0.3	1.4
TQ13	57	80	-	21	0.2	1.4
TQ14	54	76	5	38	0.3	1.4
TQ15	53	76	9	23	0.2	1.4
TQ16	70	102	4	27	0.2	1.5
TQ17	50	86	3	20	0.4	1.7
TQ18	41	59	10	23	0.3	1.5
TQ19	39	54	-	34	0.3	1.4
TQ20	39	70	1	20	0.3	1.8
TQ21	33	69	1	26	0.4	2.1
TQ22	53	88	2	26	0.2	1.7
TQ23	50	83	-	19	0.2	1.7
TQ24	37	59	1	12	0.2	1.6
TQ25	32	40	-	14	0.3	1.3
TQ26	35	58	-	16	0.3	1.7
TQ27	38	60	1	20	0.3	1.6
TQ28	42	62	-	15	0.2	1.5
TOT	706	1500	47	591	0.1	2.1

Table 4: O Order measures of THESSCITY 4.

	1	2	3
	MMD	MRRA	min RRA
TH/CITY.1-2	8.37	0.99	0.577
THESSUP.1-2	9.36	1.44	1.02

THESSTUR	8.79	1.19	0.70
THESSJEW	7.21	1.16	0.676
THESSGR	6.16	1.07	0.58
M1. 1-2	3.12	0.73	0.415
M2. 1-2	3.94	0.81	0.417
THESSCITY.3	7.68	0.91	0.51
THESSUP. 3	9.36	1.44	1.02
THESSCITY.4	6.79	0.81	0.50
THESSUP. 4	8.71	1.32	0.81
THESSCITY.5	7.03	0.87	0.487
THESSUP. 5	7.24	1.09	0.76

	4	5	6	
	Max RAA	RRAE	M.CON	
TH/CITY.1-2	1.886	0.135	3.47	
THESSUP.1-2	2.26	0.540	3.28	
THESSTUR	2.14	0.119	3.27	
THESSJEW	2.183	-0.322	3.31	
THESSGR	1.78	0.037	3.15	
M1. 1-2	1.245	-0.089	3.50	
M2. 1-2	1.59	-1.20	3.97	
THESSCITY.3	1.59	0.023	3.79	
THESSUP. 3	2.26	0.512	9.36	Max RRA-Min RRA
THESSCITY.4	1.38	0.204	4.59	THESSCITY.1-2 1.309
THESSUP. 4	2.38	0.299	3.34	THESSCITY.3 1.080
THESSCITY.5	1.58	-0.172	4.25	THESSCITY.4 0.880
THESSUP. 5	1.62	0.336	3.31	THESSCITY.5 1.093

Table 5: Mean Mean Depth (MMD), Mean Real Relative Asymmetry(MRRA) and RRA Entropy (RRAE) of all systems and subsystems.

Table 6: "Homogeneity" of the spatial structures.

the urban system than the pre-1917 plans as well as the modern one [tables 7(c),(d) and 8(c) and (d)].

MMD	(THESSUP.1-2 -THESSUP.4)=0.65	(a)
MRRA	(THESSUP.1-2 -THESSUP.4)=0.12	(b)
MMD	(THESSCITY.1-2 -THESSCITY.4)=1.58	(c)
MRRA	(THESSCITY.1-2 -THESSCITY.4)=0.18	(d)

Table 7. The transition to the Neoclassical plan.

MMD	(THESSUP.1-2 -THESSUP.5)=2.12	(a)
MRRA	(THESSUP.1-2 -THESSUP.5)=0.35	(b)
MMD	(THESSCITY.1-2 -THESSCITY.5)=1.35	(c)
MRRA	(THESSCITY.1-2 -THESSCITY.5)=0.12	(d)

Table 8. The transition to the modern plan.

The MMD and MRRA are the lowest for the Greek and the highest for the Turkish quarters in the pre-1917 plans: the Greeks reside in the least accessible parts of the city while the Turks are the least isolated community. In the same period, market areas are the most accessible parts of the city and the highly integrated to the whole urban system (table 5, M1.1-2 and M2.1-2).

The parts are better integrated to the whole system in the neoclassical plan and worse in the "unplanned" city where there is a greater diversity of the

integration values (table 6).

The RRA Entropy decreases from the "unplanned" city to the 1891 plan, it increases with the neoclassical plan and decreases again with the modern plan (table 5, column 5): the first intervention increased the heterogeneity of the urban place, while the neoclassical plan the homogeneity. Besides, "Ano-Polis" became less homogeneous to the whole system under the neoclassical plan. The differences of entropy values concerning the whole city and "Ano-Polis" indicate that this area was and still is a deep and poorly integrated system in both cases and moreover, the whole system has become far more homogeneous than "Ano-Polis" is. With regards to the three ethnicities, they are far more homogeneous spatial systems in their own terms than as subsystems of the global structure.

MMD values are decreased for almost all planning-units in the neoclassical plan: the urban system has become less deep in its micro-scale under the neoclassical plan (tables 9 and 10 column 1).

MRRA values are decreased in the 1917 plan, too: there has been a remarkable destruction of the inner-most structure of the old, "unplanned" city-neighbourhoods and ethnoquarters (table 9).

MMD has got its least value in the Turkish neighbourhoods and the greatest one in the Greek quarters: the Greek quarters are the least integrated and the Turkish ones the most integrated to the urban system (table 9.1):

3.02<MMDt<5.91	1.96<MMDg<4.37
2.01<MMDj<3.40	3.76<MMDm<4.48

(table 9.1)

The least MRRA value is in the Turkish quarters, too, and the highest one in the Greek areas: again, the Greek quarters are the least integrated and the Turkish ones the most integrated urban areas (table 9.2):

$$\begin{array}{ll} 0.71 < \text{MRRA} < 1.50 & 0.52 < \text{MRRAg} < 1.17 \\ 0.53 < \text{MRRAj} < 0.83 & 0.86 < \text{MRRAm} < 1.25 \end{array}$$

(table 9.2)

The 1891 plan increased the MMD and MRRA values of the quarters TQ6, TQ, and TQ20 where the intervention took place: the city-quarters affected became less integrated to the whole urban system (table 9).

The most homogeneous neighbourhoods are the Greek ones and the least homogeneous the Turkish ones (table 9.3).

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Max RRAt} - \text{Min RRAt} = 2.647 - 0.372 = 2.275 \\ \text{Max RRAG} - \text{Min RRAG} = 2.007 - 1.359 = 0.648 \\ \text{Max RRAj} - \text{Min RRAj} = 1.615 - 0.248 = 1.367 \\ \text{Max RRAm} - \text{Min RRAm} = 1.956 - 0.459 = 1.497 \end{array}$$

(table 9.3)

5.2.2. Control values

All four major systems and four subsystems have control values greater than 1.00 and this indicates that they are all strong control spaces.

There is a 0.10 increase in control values from the "unplanned" city to the

1891 plan, 0.04 from the 1891 to 1917 plan and 0.06 from the 1917 plan to the mid '70s plan. 0.14 increase of CV before the 1917 plan and 0.06 increase after the 1917 plan. Total increase of CV:0.20. "Ano-Polis" increases its CV by 0.00, 0.03 and 0.03 respectively, which is reasonable since its structure has been slightly altered during the whole period. Now the CVs of this area are consistently lower than the whole city's values -the difference in the pre-1917 plan is 0.37 and in the mid '70s plan 0.41. This reflects the major changes with respect to the lower parts of the city (table 11).

	MMD	MRRA	Min RRA	Max RRA
TQ1	3.90	1.08	0.731	1.620
TQ2	4.78	0.95	0.608	1.585
TQ3	4.03	1.04	0.574	1.624
TQ4	3.90	0.98	0.624	1.791
TQ5	4.14	0.90	0.470	1.349
TQ6	3.02/3.75	0.78/1.0	0.53/0.6	1.36/1.9
TQ7	1.96/2.5	0.52/0.9	0.31/0.57	0.92/1.5
TQ8	2.01	0.53	0.25	0.75
TQ9	3.40	0.77	0.45	1.28
TQ10	3.29	0.66	0.37	1.02
TQ11	3.99	1.25	0.85	1.96
TQ12	4.48	1.17	0.83	1.64
TQ13	-	-	-	-
TQ14	5.45	1.35	0.94	2.41
TQ15	5.91	1.50	0.99	2.65
TQ16	5.85	1.35	0.87	2.43
TQ17	3.58	0.81	0.42	1.54
TQ18	3.48	0.84	0.39	1.34
TQ19	4.37	1.17	0.67	2.01
TQ20	3.6/4.8	0.9/1.2	0.54/0.8	1.4/2.1

TQ21	2.93	0.73	0.46	1.19
TQ22	-	-	-	-
TQ23	3.76	0.86	0.46	1.29
TQ24	3.32	0.83	0.49	1.62
TQ25	4.45	1.32	0.90	2.28
TQ26	3.20	0.80	0.43	1.34
TQ27	3.02	0.71	0.37	1.12
TQ28	3.78	0.94	0.52	1.56

Table 9. Mean Mean Depth (MMD) and Mean Real Relative Asymmetry values in THESSCITY.1-2 and THESSCITY.3.

	MMD	MRRA	Min RRA	Max RRA
TQ1	4.44	1.28	0.810	2.633
TQ2	4.14	0.81	0.481	1.619
TQ3	4.35	1.11	0.629	1.619
TQ4	3.56	0.94	0.571	1.411
TQ5	3.34	0.75	0.335	1.151
TQ6	3.17	0.81	0.51	1.373
TQ7	2.18	0.67	0.342	0.986
TQ8	2.54	0.65	0.391	1.086
TQ9	2.54	0.65	0.391	1.089
TQ10	2.29	0.68	0.403	1.085
TQ11	2.63	0.67	0.318	0.909
TQ12	2.95	0.73	0.377	1.271
TQ13	3.81	0.93	0.568	1.834
TQ14	4.88	1.10	0.643	1.727
TQ15	3.34	0.88	0.529	1.507
TQ16	4.95	1.10	0.679	1.582

TQ17	4.31	1.13	0.706	1.634
TQ18	3.59	0.97	0.353	2.507
TQ19	3.34	0.88	0.530	1.507
TQ20	-	--	-	-
TQ21	2.70	0.68	0.431	1.050
TQ22	2.65	0.66	0.402	1.076
TQ23	3.04	0.78	0.481	1.209
TQ24	3.21	0.84	0.530	1.307
TQ25	3.47	0.99	0.488	1.836
TQ26	2.35	0.65	0.312	1.055
TQ27	3.63	0.89	0.485	1.454
TQ28	2.43	0.60	0.353	0.882

Table 10. Mean Mean Depth (MMD) and Mean Real Relative Asymmetry (MRRRA) in THESSCITY.4 (Neoclassical Plan).

	1	2	3
	MCV	Max CV	Min CV
TH/CITY.1-2	1.47	7.817	0.048
THESSUP.1-2	1.20	2.95	0.200
THESSGR	1.34	3.367	0.167
THESSTUR	1.31	7.683	0.125
THESSJEW	1.41	4.143	0.125
M1. 1-2	1.54	3.119	0.125
M2. 1-2	1.45	4.841	0.210
THESSCITY. 3	1.57	8.995	0.490
THESSUP. 3	1.20	2.95	0.200
THESSCITY.4	1.61	9.97	0.32

THESSUP. 4	1.23	4.04	0.54
THESSCITY.5	1.67	8.55	0.37
THESSUP. 5	1.26	2.95	0.63

Table 11. Aggregate Control Values. MCV: Mean Control Value. Max CV: Maximum Control Value. Min CV: Minimum

The Jewish and market areas have the highest CVs, then the Greek and Turkish ones (table 11.1).

There is a remarkable difference in CVs in the Turkish and market areas and this reflects the different principles underlying the overall spatial structure (in THESSCITY.1-2:dCV=0.74 and THESSCITY.3:dCV=0.75, in table 11.1).

	1	2	3
	MCV	Max CV	Min CV
TQ1	1.12	1.833	0.500
TQ2	1.19	2.500	0.268
TQ3	1.10	1.783	0.500
TQ4	1.22	2.333	0.310
TQ5	1.28	3.676	0.300
TQ6	1.11/1.41	1.97/2.93	0.48/0.25
TQ7	1.32/1.40	2.04/2.93	0.29/0.25
TQ8	1.44	2.893	0.254
TQ9	1.42	3.043	0.254
TQ10	1.36	3.478	0.167
TQ11	1.09	2.083	0.583
TQ12	1.13	2.00	0.400

TQ13	1.00	4.559	0.200
TQ14	1.21	2.700	0.200
TQ15	1.12	2.150	0.333
TQ16	1.20	2.50	0.200
TQ17	-	-	-
TQ18	1.47	3.833	0.167
TQ19	1.39	2.500	1.167
TQ20	1.15/1.33	1.98/3.03	0.45/0.25
TQ21	1.49	3.167	0.222
TQ22	1.16	2.000	0.343
TQ23	1.26	3.042	0.311
TQ24	1.24	2.228	0.310
TQ25	1.16	2.000	0.500
TQ26	1.50	3.543	0.225
TQ27	1.66	4.460	0.143
TQ28	1.15	2.308	0.333

Table 12. Control Values (CV) of city-quarters (TQs) in THESSCITY.1-2 and THESSCITY.3.

	MCV
Turkish TQs	1.31
Greek TQs	1.34
Jewish TQs	1.41
Market TQs	1.95

Table 11.1 CVs of TQs in THESSCITY.1-2 and THESSCITY.3

	1	2	3
	MCV	Max CV	Min CV
TQ1	1.13	1.750	0.333
TQ2	1.22	2.652	0.268
TQ3	1.14	2.000	0.450
TQ4	1.23	2.750	0.272
TQ5	1.37	4.375	0.3750
TQ6	1.19	2.317	0.367
TQ7	1.31	2.200	0.310
TQ8	1.43	2.367	0.268
TQ9	1.43	2.367	0.268
TQ10	1.41	2.367	0.309
TQ11	1.29	2.983	0.400
TQ12	1.21	2.383	0.268
TQ13	1.74	4.459	0.160
TQ14	1.14	2.933	0.417
TQ15	1.333	1.833	0.250
TQ16	1.140	2.700	0.400
TQ17	1.17	2.333	0.367
TQ18	1.38	2.760	0.268
TQ19	1.13	1.917	0.417
TQ20	1.13	1.917	0.417
TQ21	1.51	3.530	0.143
TQ22	1.21	2.010	0.310
TQ23	1.15	1.85	0.250
TQ24	1.17	1.183	0.250
TQ25	1.17	2.750	0.500

TQ26	1.30	2.45	0.367
TQ27	1.42	3.85	0.183
TQ28	1.65	3.417	0.125

Table 13. Control Values (CV) of THESSCITY.4 (Neoclassical Plan).

	1	2	3	4
	(GV)	(CH)	(I)	(PR)
	RRA/CV	TC/CV	CON/RecRR	RTC/rRRA
			A	
CITY1-2	0.15	0.61	0.33	0.49
T/UP1-2	0.18	0.42	0.47	0.58
T/TUR	0.16	0.58	0.39	0.50
T/JEW	0.14	0.52	0.52	0.46
T/GR	0.16	0.58	0.60	0.65
M1.1-2	0.46	0.79	0.82	0.81
M2.1-2	0.19	0.67	0.67	0.45
CITY.3	0.14	0.65	0.22	0.29
T/UP.3	0.18	0.42	0.37	0.59
CITY.4	0.15	0.63	0.46	0.45
T/UP.4	0.15	0.42	0.37	0.59
CITY.5	0.15	0.67	0.42	0.36
T/UP.5	0.16	0.59	0.54	0.69

Table 14. Aggregate B Order measures for all four urban systems and subsystems.

	(GV)	(CH)	(I)	(PR)
	1	2	3	4
TQ1	0.26	0.50	0.67	0.57

TQ2	0.27	0.60	0.55	0.70
TQ3	0.49	0.68	0.85	0.89
TQ4	0.31	0.54	0.74	0.50
TQ5	0.34	0.68	0.64	0.84
TQ6	0.3/0.2	0.7/0.6	0.8/0.7	0.9/0.8
TQ7	0.7/0.3	0.9/0.7	0.9/0.8	0.9/0.8
TQ8	0.86	0.92	0.98	0.94
TQ9	0.34	0.72	0.74	0.73
TQ10	0.46	0.78	0.76	0.85
TQ11	0.32	0.55	0.75	0.75
TQ12	0.24	0.59	0.60	0.78
TQ13	0.25	0.61	0.64	0.73
TQ14	0.24	0.28	0.61	0.63
TQ15	0.25	0.46	0.68	0.44
TQ16	0.20	0.29	0.61	0.74
TQ17	0.33	0.71	0.74	0.74
TQ18	0.44	0.75	0.77	0.83
TQ19	0.35	0.63	0.76	0.53
TQ20	0.4/0.3	0.7/0.6	0.8/0.6	0.8/0.5
TQ21	0.39	0.60	0.63	0.83
TQ22	-	-	-	-
TQ23	0.37	0.72	0.76	0.79
TQ24	0.46	0.83	0.86	0.78
TQ25	0.23	0.58	0.73	0.67
TQ26	0.33	0.75	0.81	0.68
TQ27	0.49	0.82	0.84	0.86
TQ28	0.14	0.45	0.86	0.78

Table 15. B Order measures of TQs in THESSCITY.1-2 and THESSCITY.3

(GV): Global Value

(CH): Choice

(I): Intelligibility

(PR): Predictability

5.3. B Order measures

The global values of the urban systems ($GV=RRA/CV$) remain almost stable with a slight reduction in the neoclassical plan. The same applies for "Ano-Polis". These values as well as those concerning the city's ethnoquarters are consistently poor for all pre-and-post 1917 plans if compared with the average of urban layouts (0.68, table 14, column 1).

The Choice of the whole urban system is increased by the neoclassical plan and furthermore by the modern plan. The same applies for "Ano-Polis". In the pre-1917 plans the lowest values are met in Jewish quarters, then the Greek, the Turkish ones and the highest values in market areas (table 14, column 2). Inhabitant movement has been favoured by the neoclassical and modern plans, while in the pre-1917 plans inhabitants are almost excluded from the Jewish and Greek areas, and minimally accepted in Turkish ones; in contrast, they could easily move in market areas.

All four systems have lower intelligibility than the average of the urban layouts (0.71), but nevertheless, the neoclassical plan has improved it consistently and this, although slightly reduced, is maintained up to the modern plan. In contrast, "Ano-Polis" has acquired its higher intelligibility under the modern plan; this, again, is reasonable since the neoclassical plan left the area almost unaffected.

	1	2	3	4
	(GV)	(CH)	(I)	(PR)
TQ1	0.18	0.31	0.83	0.49
TQ2	0.35	0.68	0.79	0.70
TQ3	0.30	0.50	0.71	0.92
TQ4	0.25	0.60	0.59	0.71
TQ5	0.34	0.78	0.77	0.78
TQ6	.	.	.	.

TQ7	0.65	0.80	0.90	0.90
TQ8	0.55	0.81	0.84	0.89
TQ9	0.55	0.81	0.84	0.89
TQ10	0.50	0.82	0.81	0.85
TQ11	0.58	0.85	0.81	0.89
TQ12	0.47	0.75	0.90	0.76
TQ13	0.18	0.53	0.56	0.42
TQ14	0.21	0.54	0.62	0.72
TQ15	0.16	0.31	0.46	0.42
TQ16	0.24	0.45	0.46	0.85
TQ17	0.18	0.56	0.72	0.51
TQ18	-	-	-	-
TQ19	0.17	0.58	0.50	0.84
TQ20	0.29	0.60	0.50	0.84

Table 16. B Order measures of 'planning-units' in THESSCITY 4

The "intelligibility" of "ethnoquarters" in pre-1917 plans is higher in market areas, then the Greek quarters, the Jewish and the Turkish ones, that is market areas are the most intelligible of all subsystems. Market areas performed spaces of strong "legibility" as well, that is they allowed people to orient themselves in space better than in any other part of the city (table 14, column 3).

"Predictability" (movement of strangers) is lower than the average (0.54) in all four systems, it is reduced by the 1891 plan, remarkably increased by the neoclassical plan and noticeably decreased in the modern plan. "Ano-Polis" has this spatial property higher than the average and increased it in the modern plan. In "ethno-quarters predictability is best in market areas, then the Greek, the Turkish and finally the Jewish ones (tables 15 and 16).

Summarising, the city within-the-walls has been drastically affected in

terms of its open public space structure by the neoclassical plan and to a less extent by the 1891, modern and post-modern plans. The major changes happened in the lower part of the city and under the neoclassical plan.

In the pre-1917 city the least gridiron are the market and Turkish quarters, then the Greek and finally the Jewish ones.

After the 1891 plan the system typologically remains stable, close to the structure of the "organic" cities.

In the pre-1917 city the least regularised are the Turkish areas, then the Jewish, the Greek and finally the market areas.

The gridiron of the plan is increased remarkably by the neoclassical plan and to a less extent by the modern plan.

The local attributes of the system (connectivity) are improved essentially by the neoclassical plan, whereas the modern plan slightly reduced them. In the pre-1917 plans the best attributes are found in the market areas, then the Jewish, the Greek, and finally the Turkish quarters.

The neoclassical plan integrated best the city's parts to the whole, while there is a slight inverse trend with the modern plan. In "Ano-Polis" there is an increasing integration to the whole system up to the modern plan.

In the pre-1917 city the Greeks reside in the least accessible parts of the system, then the Jews and finally the Turks.

Market areas are the most accessible part of the global structure. Besides, the "planning-units" in the neoclassical plan are better integrated to the global structure than the "ethnoquarters" in the pre-1917 city.

The 1891 plan increased the heterogeneity of the urban space, while the neoclassical plan the homogeneity."Ano-Polis" became less homogeneous to the whole system under the neoclassical plan.

The three distinct ethnicities, although their space is less homogeneous

than in the planning units of the 1917 plan, are far more homogeneous spatial systems in their own terms than the overall structure and this applies even more to the market areas: the Greek quarters are the most homogeneous, then the Jewish and finally the Turkish ones.

The 1917 plan increased the integration of the old distinct parts to the global structure by a) decreasing the mean depth and relative asymmetry of almost all the city-neighbourhoods and b) re-articulating the inner-most structure of the old "ethnoquarters". The integration of the parts to the whole increases from the Greek to Jewish, Turkish and market areas.

The whole city acquires all the more better local dynamic attributes (control values). "Ano-Polis" has got increasingly better attributes under the neoclassical and modern plans, but nevertheless, these attributes remain much poorer than those of the whole system. Hence, the local dynamic attributes of Lower city have been far more improved by the neoclassical and modern plans. The best local dynamic attributes are in the market and Jewish quarters; the Greek and Turkish follow.

The poor global values of all four systems as well as their subsystems - "Ano-Polis" in all plans and "ethnoquarters"- indicate that high control values are not accompanied by strong global integration.

The inhabitant movement and distribution of people is increased by the neoclassical plan and even more by the modern plan; in pre-1917 plans they are less encouraged in Jewish quarters, the Greek and then the Turkish ones; market areas favour most inhabitant movement.

Intelligibility has been improved consistently by the neoclassical plan and is maintained slightly reduced by now.

"Ano-Polis" is now more intelligible than ever.

In the pre-1917 city market areas are the most "intelligible" and "legible" places, then the Turkish quarters, the Jewish and finally the Greek ones.

The neoclassical plan increases remarkably the "movement interface" and this is slightly reduced by the modern plan. In contrast, "Ano-Polis" increased this property all the more . In the pre-1917 city the movement interface is best in market areas, then the Turkish, the Greek and finally the Jewish quarters.

CHAPTER VI: SYNTACTIC ANALYSIS

6.1. The 1890 and 1891 Plans

6.1.1. Integration

6.1.2. Control - Intelligibility

6.1.3. Choice -Movement Interface

6.2 The 1917 Plan

6.2.1 Integration

6.2.2. Control - Intelligibility

6.2.3. Choice -Movement Interface

6.3. The mid 1970s Plan

6.3.1. Integration

6.3.2. Control - Intelligibility

6.3.3. Choice -Movement Interface

6.4. The late 1980s Plan

6.4.1. Integration

6.4.2. Control - Intelligibility

6.4.3. Choice - Movement Interface

6.1. The 1890 and 1891 plans (axial maps 1.1 and 1.2)

6.1.2. Integration (maps 2,3,4,5,6.)

The Integration core consists of 50 lines (the 5% most integrated lines of the city, map 2).

a) The first four of them form a square in the gravity centre of the city. The core makes direct links between the carrier and the city's most integrated parts. This applies mainly for Egnatia St., the main commercial street of the city that stretches between its two most important entrances.

b) The residual lines provide condensation to the primary rectangular core. The links between the three parallel streets (Egnatia, St. Demetrious and Kassandros Sts.) grow stronger by a set of integrating lines perpendicular to the first.

c) Although the city has got an irregular structure in 1890, its core largely coincides with the initial hellenistic and roman grid.

d) The major gap in the heart of the core is identical to the hellenistic "Agora" or roman "Forum".

e) The most condensed part of the core is focused in the lower quarters of the Turkish area (the administration centre); however, the core hardly penetrates the first quarters upwards Kassandros St. (the Turkish purely residential areas).

f) The core integrates the major Turkish public buildings. In contrast, only two out of thirty three Jewish public buildings coincide with the core and almost none of the Greek ones.

Map (2) also shows the 50% most segregated lines.